

Predictive Cognitive
Maintenance Decision
Support System
PreCoM

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Executive Summary

The PreCoM system will consist of different modules, namely the PreCoM sense module for data collection, pre-processing and communication, PreCoM AI for further data analysis and predictive analytics, PreCoM AR/PLIV for supporting the maintenance actions by applying innovative augmented reality technology and PreCoM connect for integrating all before mentioned modules into production planning and maintenance planning.

This deliverable describes and illustrates data-driven statistical models to improve the diagnosis and prediction in the presence of uncertainty (different types of machines or components, working conditions, etc.).

We present the statistical model and we validate it by conducting a proof of concept with two well-known databases: MIMOSA and Mill-NASA.

For the MIMOSA database, two software tools will be introduced. First tool is PreVib, a software module which implements a mechanistic model for predicting the vibration level, when using vibration-based maintenance (VBM). Its aim is to detect deviations in the condition of a component at an early stage in order to act for keeping the probability of failure of machine/significant component low until a condition-based replacement is done. The second software tool is ProLife, an implementation of a probabilistic approach. The goal of ProLife is to assess the probability of failure of a component/equipment and the residual lifetime of a component/equipment when its condition monitoring level, e.g. vibration level is significantly high. These two software modules will be used in PreCoM for rotating components.

For the Mill-NASA dataset, we develop statistical models using two approaches. The first model is based in time series analysis (TSA). TSA can predict the time when a variable of interest (target parameter such as vibration in a critical component, such as a cutting tool) overcomes a specific threshold. This event may suggest tool replacement or a specific maintenance action because of an excessive wear or changes in product quality. The second model is based in lifetime data analysis (LTA) techniques, such as proportional hazard (PH) models or accelerated failure time (AFT) models. We apply these models to estimate relevant parameters like, for instance, the mean residual lifetime (MRL) depending on working conditions and the probability of failure at some future time. We also apply LTA methods to predict the remaining operation time of the machine. Both LTA and TSA approaches will be used for non-rotating components.

The proof of concept illustrates how the proposed statistical models can be applied to real data. The statistical models should be evaluated on the data gathered at the demonstration companies of the PreCoM project as soon as they become available.

List of acronyms

AFT	Accelerated Failure Time
BDA	Big Data Analytics
CBM	Condition-Based Maintenance
CM	Condition Monitoring
D	Deliverable
MRL	Mean Residual Lifetime
OEE	Overall Equipment Effectiveness
PdM	Predictive Maintenance
PH	Proportional Hazard
PLIV	Production Line Information Visualisation
TP	Target Parameters
TQMain	Total Quality Maintenance
TSA	Time Series Analysis
VBM	Vibration-based maintenance
WP	Work Package

List of keywords

Big Data Analytics
Condition Monitoring
Critical Components
Decision-support System
Demo-companies
Industry 4.0
Lifetimes/Failure Data
Manufacturing Systems
Maintenance Optimization
Predictive Maintenance
Statistical Models
Target Parameter
Time Series

1. Introduction

In this document we present data-driven statistical models that can improve diagnosis and prediction for the three demo-companies in PreCoM. Specifically, in Section 2 we consider two different approaches to be applied to non-rotating components: time series analysis (TSA) and lifetime data analysis (LTA). TSA (Section 2.1) and LTA (Section 2.2) may not only contribute to the preliminary inspection of the data gathered by the sensors, but also to diagnosis and prediction when the information on the machine typology or the working environmental situation is either limited or nearly non-existent. Although most information on failure times, maintenance performances and product quality is still unavailable, we expected it to be accessible for use in LTA and TSA during the project. In the worst case scenario, the proposed models will be applied using proxy variables for the missing records combined with expert knowledge. In Section 2.3 a proof of concept is presented using two datasets, MIMOSA and Mill-NASA, which resemble the ideal situation for demonstration companies regarding the statistical information. The proof of concept illustrates the application of the proposed statistical models to the real data that will be supplied by the end users.

Sections 3 and 4 describe and illustrate two software modules – PreVib and ProLife – which will be applied to rotating components.

In Section 5 we consider the aforementioned statistical models in the specific settings of the PreCoM demonstration companies.

Furthermore, FMECA models will be used to identify machine top problems, partition a machine, analyse component failures (identify root-causes, effects on system operations and component criticalities) and identify significant components (components of dangerous or expensive failures) to provide effective maintenance efforts on the right components. See in this respect Section 6.

Some conclusions are provided in Section 7.

2. Statistical models for life time data and time series analysis

This section aims to develop the preliminary phase of the implementation of vibration-based maintenance (VBM). Statistical models, particularly TSA and LTA, are useful tools to carry out VBM within an industry 4.0 framework. This first phase, called "offline", consists of using a well-known data set to determine patterns, features, characteristics using statistical tools (descriptive analysis, statistical modelling, prediction, ...).

The main objective of this section is to provide estimation and prediction of 1) time of failure or stoppage for the machine critical component and 2) the time when a variable of interest (target parameter) overcomes a specific threshold. To this end, we consider LTA and TSA techniques to provide statistical information useful to Condition Based Maintenance (CBM) in a manufacturing industry.

2.1. Time series analysis (TSA)

CM signal acquired through sensors and loading in a Savvy platform is a sequence taken at successive spaced points in time, that is called time series, see Hamilton (1994). TSA can be used to estimate statistical parameters of interest, such as the mean and variance related with time series of the target parameters (TP) in a critical component.

TSA allows to:

- identify patterns in data (trends and seasonal variation),
- model the data,
- forecast from previous patterns,
- evaluate how does an event change the time series.

Typically, in TSA, a process $Y(t)$ is assumed to consist of several sub-components:

- a trend, $\mu(t)$, that represents a deterministic tendency,
- a periodicity, $P(t)$, that represents regularly repeating behaviour,
- a seasonality, $S(t)$, that represents longer term patterns,
- a random error, $e(t)$, that captures the effects of local short term changes which are not explained by the longer term patterns.

Formally,

$$Y(t) = \mu(t) + P(t) + S(t) + e(t).$$

ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) models are a general class of time series models, based on the description of the autocorrelation in the data. Let $\{Y_t\}$ be a given time series of data where Y_t denote the observation at time t . An ARMA(p, q) model is given by:

$$Y_t = \mu + \Phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \dots + \Phi_p Y_{t-p} + e_t - \theta_1 e_{t-1} - \dots - \theta_q e_{t-q}.$$

Parameters specify the deterministic (μ), autoregressive (Φ), moving average (θ), and error (e) components (e_t is assumed to be white noise). The values p and q represent the orders of the AR (AutoRegressive) and MA (Moving Average) terms, respectively. The ARMA(p, q) model can be written in compact notation as:

$$\Phi_p(L)Y_t = \theta_q(L)e_t,$$

where L denotes the lag operator, $LY_t = Y_{t-1}$, $\Phi_p(L) = (1 - \Phi_1 L - \dots - \Phi_p L^p)$ and $\theta_q(L) = (1 - \theta_1 L - \dots - \theta_q L^q)$.

We say that $\{Y_t\}$ is an ARIMA process of order p, d, q , written, $Y_t \sim \text{ARIMA}(p, d, q)$, if the d th difference of Y_t is an stationary, invertible ARMA process of order p, q , that is:

$$\Phi_p(L)(1 - B)^d Y_t = \theta_q(L)e_t.$$

The stationarity and invertibility conditions for the model are that the complex roots of $\Phi_p(L) = 0$ and $\theta_q(L) = 0$ lie outside the unit circle.

An ARIMAX model assumes an ARIMA model with a covariate X_t . Formally, the model is given by:

$$\Phi_p(L)(1 - B)^d Y_t = \beta_t X_t + \theta_q(L)e_t.$$

2.2. Lifetime data analysis (LTA)

The main goal of LTA in PreCoM Project is to estimate the probability distribution of the remaining operation time of the targeted machine/component. This probability distribution allows us to calculate relevant parameters such as the mean residual lifetime, future probabilities of failure or stoppage, and specific quantiles of the residual life. The estimation of such parameters will be performed through proper statistical methods for the analysis of lifetimes or failure data (Kalbfleisch and Prentice 2011). These methods are briefly outlined now.

Analysis of failure time data deals with the problem of studying the time until the happening of a failure or event of interest. For instance, vibration or temperature overtaking an established threshold may indicate the event of failure.

In what follows, T denotes a nonnegative random variable representing the failure time of an individual from a homogeneous population for simplicity in the exposition. In our practical scenarios, the distribution of T may depend on particular machine/component characteristics, working conditions, manufactured product type, etc., and these covariables will be taken into account. How to include the covariables in the model will be explained too.

The probability distribution of T can be specified in many ways, four of which are especially useful: the reliability (or survival) function, the probability density function, the failure rate (or hazard) function and the expected residual life at time t . In the following sections we describe them briefly.

2.2.1. The reliability (or survival) function

The probability that T exceeds a value t in its range defines the reliability (or survival) function. That is,

$$R(t) = P(T > t), 0 < t < \infty \quad (1)$$

If F represents the distribution function of T , $F(t) = P(T \leq t)$, then

$$R(t) = 1 - F(t), 0 < t < \infty.$$

It is verified that R is a continuous and decreasing monotone function satisfying $R(0)=1$ and $R(\infty)=0$. In addition, the p -quantile with $0 < p < 1$ of the distribution of T is defined as the value t_p verifying $F(t_p)=P(T \leq t_p)=p$, or equivalently, $t_p=F^{-1}(p)$, where F^{-1} denotes the inverse function of F . Quantiles may be seen as cutpoints dividing the range of a probability distribution according to the value of p that may be used to decide when maintenance tasks must be carried out too. Depending on values of p , the decision of maintenance will be more conservative or more risky.

2.2.2. The probability density function

The density function can be obtained from the distribution function F as its derivative:

$$f(t)=F'(t) \tag{2}$$

In Figure 1 depict an example of a density function (left panel) and its corresponding distribution function (right panel).

Figure 1: Density and distribution functions.

2.2.3. The failure rate (or hazard) function

The failure rate (or hazard) function h specifies the instantaneous rate at which a failure occurs at time t . It is satisfied that $h(t)=f(t)/R(t)$. Now integrating, we obtain the cumulative failure rate function H :

$$H(t)=\int_{[0,t]} h(x)dx \tag{3}$$

Furthermore, the next equality is verified (using Eq.2):

$$H(t)=-\log(1-F(t)).$$

Decreasing hazard functions appear when the probability of failure is high at early stages. Such a decreasing shape may be provoked by the existence of defective components in the production. Constant hazard functions are common when failures are due to random phenomena like accidents. Finally, increasing hazard functions appear in the presence of wear in the component or machine of interest. If these three cases are combined, the well-known bathtub curve appears (see Figure 2). The first part (a) corresponds to early failure; the second one (b) is associated to constant failure risks where the machine or component do not suffer the passing of time and the last one (c) corresponds to wear-out failures.

Figure 2: Bathub curve representing the three usual types of hazard functions defined in Eq. 3.

2.2.4. Mean residual lifetime (MRL)

In survival or reliability studies, the mean residual life or residual life expectancy is an important characteristic of the model. So, the expected residual life at time t is another representation of the failure time distribution that may be useful in the PreCoM project. It is defined as the conditional expectation:

$$r(t) = E(T - t \mid T \geq t)$$

The mean residual life at time t can be also written as:

$$r(t) = \int_{[t, \infty)} R(u) du / R(t) \quad (4)$$

where $R(\cdot)$ is the survival function (Eq. 1).

The survival function can be written in terms of the expected residual life as follows (Kalbfleisch and Prentice 2011):

$$R(t) = [r(0)/r(t)] \exp\{-\int_{[0, t]} du/r(u)\} \quad (5)$$

For location-scale based parametric distributions (exponential, Weibull, lognormal), we denote the location parameter by μ and the scale by σ . Note that using Eq. 5 the mean life, $\mu = r(0)$, is the total area under survival curve:

$$\mu = E(T) = \int_{[0, \infty)} R(u) du$$

Also the variance of T is related to the survival function by

$$\sigma^2 = \text{Var}(T) = 2 \int_{[0, \infty)} u R(u) du - [\int_{[0, \infty)} R(u) du]^2$$

In the following Section we specify all the aforementioned important target for the Weibull model, which is one of the most widely used parametric models for the analysis of lifetime data.

2.2.5. The Weibull distribution model

Certain parametric models have been used in the literature devoted to failure time data. Exponential or Weibull distributions are the most commonly used models for T. These distributions admit closed-form expressions for tail area probabilities and, therefore, simple formulas for reliability and failure rate functions. Since the Exponential model is a particular case of the Weibull distribution, we describe only the latter of these two distributions.

T follows a Weibull distribution with scale parameter $a > 0$ and shape parameter $b > 0$, and it is represented as $T \sim \text{Weibull}(a,b)$, if the density function is:

$$f(t) = ab(at)^{b-1} \exp\{-(at)^b\}, t > 0.$$

In this case, $F(t) = 1 - \exp\{-(at)^b\}$, and hence the reliability and failure rate functions can be written as $R(t) = \exp\{-(at)^b\}$ and $h(t) = ab(at)^{b-1}$, respectively. The particular case $b=1$ corresponds to the Exponential model with constant failure rate function $h(t) = a$. See Figure 3 for graphical details on Weibull density functions f (left) and distribution functions F (right) when $a=1$ and $b=0.5, 1, 1.5, 2$ and 3.44 .

Figure 3: Weibull density functions (left) and distribution functions (right) with $b=0.5, 1, 1.5, 2$ and 3.44 and $a=1$.

Figure 4: Failure rate functions for Weibull distribution with $b = 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2$ and 3.44 and $a=1$.

Several failure rate functions can be obtained according to the values of the parameter b when $a=1$, see Figure 4. Therefore, different situations appear:

- If $b < 1$ then h is a decreasing function.
- If $b = 1$, the hazard function is constant. It does not depend on time. In this case, the Weibull distribution is equal to the Exponential one.
- If $b > 1$ then h is an increasing function.

In addition, the p -quantile of Weibull distribution is determined as follows:

$$t_p = (1/a)[- \log(1-p)]^{1/b}$$

In particular, percentile 63.2% is the value $1/a$ and it can be interpreted as the time up to which 63.2% of the units have failed. As aforementioned, the maintenance decision could be more conservative or risky depending on the selected percentile.

The mean residual life function of the Weibull model equals

$$r(t) = \Gamma(1/b; (ta)^b) / (ab \exp\{-(at)^b\}) \quad (6)$$

where $\Gamma(s;x) = \int_{[x,\infty]} u^{s-1} e^{-u} du$ is the incomplete gamma function. Thus, the mean residual time can be easily evaluated given the parameters a and b .

In our practical (end users) scenarios, the time to failure or stoppage may depend on the machine working conditions, product type and other covariables. The usual Weibull regression model is the one specifying that the scale parameter is a certain transformation (such as the exponential transform) of a linear predictor $a(x) = \exp(B'x)$ say, where x denotes the vector of available covariates (product being manufactured, working conditions, machine characteristics, etc.) and B' denotes the transposed vector of regression coefficients to be estimated from the failure time data.

2.2.6. *Proportional hazard (PH) model*

As mentioned, the time T to failure or stoppage may depend on some covariables. The usual Weibull regression model specifies that the scale parameter is a certain transformation (such as the exponential transform) of a linear predictor, $a(x) = \exp(B'x)$. Alternatively, $\exp(bB'x)$ is the factor multiplying the Weibull-type baseline failure rate function $h_0(t) = bt^{b-1}$ under working conditions x . Thus, the Weibull regression model falls under the umbrella of the proportional hazard (PH) model, which specifies that different covariate values will entail failure rate functions which run proportionally along time. This implies that the covariate effects may be interpreted as factors which multiply the failure rate. Interestingly, the proportional hazards model allows for distributions other than the Weibull; indeed, the semiparametric approach provides estimates for the regression coefficients when the baseline failure rate function is left unspecified.

2.2.7. *Accelerated failure time (AFT) model*

The Weibull regression model also belongs to the family of accelerated failure time (AFT) models. Under this viewpoint, $\exp(B'x)$ is interpreted as a factor which accelerates time leading to an earlier (if the factor is >1) or later (if <1) failure of the device.

For example, let A and B be two products manufactured by a specific machine, and assume that the covariate vector x reduces to the product indicator. Let $S_A(t)$ and $S_B(t)$ denote the reliability functions

for a critical component when A and B are manufactured, respectively. It could be natural to assume, according the expert-knowledge, that:

$$S_A(t) = S_B(kt)$$

where $k > 0$ is the acceleration factor. In other words, the failure times relative to the two products satisfy $kT_A = T_B$. For instance, if $k=7$, A accelerates through life about 7 times faster than B.

2.3. Proof of concept for Mill Data Set

The purpose of this section is to implement an offline condition monitoring of the critical component for Milling data set (Agogino and Goebel, 2007). Hereby, two of the main statistical approaches (LTA and TSA) have been implemented (fitted model in a sample data) and tested (predicted values in a new data).

2.3.1. Data description

NASA Ames prognostics data repository¹ is a growing source covering several sets of prognostic data contributed by universities, companies, or agencies. Datasets in the repository consist of run-to-failure time series data representing the case study under examination. Seven sets of prognostics dataset are available. In this section, we present the analysis of Milling Dataset for data-driven modelling. This data set uses problems similar to those of the PreCoM project, so it is used as proof of concept to determine which statistical techniques have the greatest potential.

Sixteen milling inserts were degraded by running them at different operating conditions (feed, material and depth of cut), see Agogino and Goebel (2007). Once the flank wear on the milling insert exceeded a standard threshold level, the tool was considered to have failed. Sixteen cases present a varying number of runs (see Appendix 1). The number of runs was dependent on the degree of flank wear measured between runs at irregular intervals up to (and sometimes beyond) a wear limit. Please see Goebel (1996) for further details about data acquisition and processing such as the basic setup of the spindle and signals from the vibration sensor.

2.3.2. Statistical methods for tool wear prediction

In an industrial process, the manufacturing of a high-quality product often involves a high-quality surface finish and dimensional accuracy. Therefore, a sharp tool must be kept at all times and tool wear has to be controlled to avoid unexpected problems in the machining process, see García-Nieto et al. (2016).

Tool wear comes in different forms. In particular, speed of cutting, more than other parameters, influence the rate of wear; depth of cut and feed rate also affect the tool life. The flank wear VB is in this experiment a generally-accepted parameter for evaluating tool wear because the tool wear may result in negative consequences on the quality of product and machine life. To address this problem, next section presents statistical models to reveal the relationship between the mill signal features and the wear degradation behaviour of milling tool. We also predict a tool wear evolution in the next future horizon using TSA following the next scheme:

1. Fit ARIMA models based on observations Y_1, \dots, Y_t .

¹ <https://ti.arc.nasa.gov/tech/dash/groups/pcoe/prognostic-data-repository/>

2. Forecast from fitted models for $t + h, h = 1, \dots, 10$.
3. Compute: point prediction (\hat{y}_{t+h}), 95% confidence interval, residual predictions $e_{t+h} = y_{t+h} - \hat{y}_{t+h}$, standard errors of prediction and probability $P(\hat{y}_{t+h} > L)$, where L is a given threshold.
4. Residual Control Chart
 - a. $y_{t+h} \gg \hat{y}_{t+h}$ value observed in the process greater than expected.
 - b. $y_{t+h} \ll \hat{y}_{t+h}$ value observed in the process lower than expected.
5. For the same case (task, material, tool, etc.): repeat the process for the new observation, $t = t + 1$.

In step 1 of the previous scheme we consider the following statistical models:

1. ARIMA(1,0,0).
2. ARIMA(1,0,0) with covariates X .
3. ARIMA(1,1,0) with covariates X .

From the point of view of regression models, the additive models (MARS, see Garcia-Nieto et al. (2016); GAM, see Hastie (2017) and Wood (2001)) can be taken into account, since they allow for estimating nonlinear relationships between the covariables and the response.

2.3.3. Flank wear prediction

This section predicts a tool wear using TSA. First of all, we estimate the ARIMA models for each type of material A and B. For simplicity, we limited the study to dichotomous predictors $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{feed}, \mathbf{DOC}, \mathbf{time}, \mathbf{change}\}$ (see Table 1 for description) and the response variable is $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{VB}$: Flank wear (measured after runs, in mm).

Table 1: Description of predictors

Covariates	Description
time	Duration of experiment (restarts for each case)
DOC	Depth of cut (mm), with two levels. The highest is the double that the lowest (does not vary for each case)
feed	Feed (mm/rev), with two levels. The highest is the double that the lowest (does not vary for each case).
change	1 if the flank wear of tool overcomes a threshold, 0 otherwise

The results of the three different fitted models computed independently for the two types of material are shown in Table 2. The columns name "LB test" shows the p-value of the Ljung-Box test statistic for examining the null hypothesis of independence in the three time series fitted ($\alpha=0.05$). The mean squared error (MSE) is a measure of the quality of an estimator/prediction and values closer to zero are better. The MSE measures the average of the squares of the errors in train and predicted data.

Table 2: Results for adjusted models

Model	Material A			Material B		
	LB test	MSE in train	MSE in predictions (h=10)	LB test	MSE in train	MSE in prediction (h=10)
1) ARIMA(1,0,0)	0.503	0.0320	0.1111	0.761	0.0963	0.1603
2) ARIMAX(1,0,0)	0.924	0.0034	0.0018	0.009	0.0028	0.0304
3) ARIMAX(1,1,0)	0.791	0.0039	0.0024	0.317	0.0025	0.0106

Models 2) and 3) are similar in MSE terms and exhibit better results than model 1). However, model 2) does not pass the LB test for material B (p-value < 0.05), therefore, we will use model 3) from now on.

Since a standard threshold level is unknown, as illustration $L = 0.6$ (mm) is considered as the recommended limit of tool replacement. Of course another threshold can be considered arbitrarily. Under the previous assumptions, Figure 5 shows 10 predicted values and 80% and 95% prediction intervals for the flank wear (for material A in left panel and material B in right panel).

Figure 5: Forecasts of Flank wear (VB) using the ARIMAX(1,1,0) model: observed VB in black, point forecasts in blue, 80% (dark grey) and 95% (light grey) prediction intervals, limit of tool replacement in red for material A (left panel) and material B (right panel).

In addition, Table 3 shows $P(\hat{y}_{t+h} > L)$, the probability that at the time $t + h$ the prediction \hat{y}_{t+h} overcomes the threshold $L = 0.6$ (mm).

Table 3: Evolution of the prediction for the following $t + h$ temporal horizons using ARIMA(1,1,0) model with covariates. Response variable is $Y=VB$.

h	Material A			Material B		
	y_{t+h}	\hat{y}_{t+h}	$P(\hat{y}_{t+h} > L)$	y_{t+h}	\hat{y}_{t+h}	$P(\hat{y}_{t+h} > L)$
1	1.14	0.921	0.811	0.12	0.171	0.012
2	0.15	0.000	0.040	0.17	0.203	0.019
3	0.28	0.070	0.072	0.20	0.246	0.031
4	0.37	0.182	0.125	0.24	0.289	0.051
5	0.48	0.332	0.230	0.32	0.334	0.081
6	0.56	0.444	0.334	0.40	0.386	0.131
7	0.70	0.557	0.453	0.45	0.432	0.188
8	0.24	0.154	0.110	0.49	0.477	0.260
9	0.40	0.264	0.177	0.58	0.523	0.343
10	0.62	0.377	0.270	0.65	0.577	0.452

Residual Control Chart

Statistical Process Control (SPC) is widely applied to monitor and improve highly integrated and automated manufacturing processes. Adopting proper SPC charts and corresponding detection mechanisms is crucial for a CM manufacturing process. This section conducts an empirical study of milling machining manufacturing processes to identify if the residual control chart (RCC) is a suitable method for complement and monitor the process. For this, once the observation y_i is available, it is possible to calculate and draw the residual $e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$ to perform statistical quality control, see Figure 6. The RCC chart assumes normally, independent and identically distributed errors to compute the lower and upper limits.

In Figure 6 the points in red are atypical with respect to the expected residual given by the adjusted model. Positive values may indicate tool wear greater than expected, while values below may be indicative, for example, of a replacement. In left panel, at times 47 and 56 the tool was replaced and the time restarted. For material B (right panel) no atypical value is observed in the training sample, but the wear is greater than expected in the test sample (an expert intervention may be required).

Figure 6: Control chart of estimated residuals (calibration data) and predictions (new data) for model 3 in material A (left panel) and material B (right panel)

2.3.4. Time series using indirect indicators

In the previous example the flank wear was observed during the experiments, it was taken out of the tool and the wear was measured with the help of a microscope. However, this measure might not be always available for different reasons (costs, no measurements, ...) and sometimes it is necessary to use indirect health indicators like the vibration monitoring. In this case, a more realistic model is to use the time series of CM signals to perform CBM of machine tools. The variables **smcAC**, **smcDC**, **vib_table**, **vib_spindle**, **AE_table**, and **AE_spindle** are curves with 9000 points each, see Figure 7.

The root mean square (RMS) for each of these curves is computed in order to have only one value. The RMS is a measure of the magnitude proportional to the energy contents of the signal.

Figure 7: Typical signatures from the different sensors observed during in 9000 instants.

Now, the process is identical to that described in the previous section. Let $Y = \text{smcDC}$ be the value of RMS computed for the signal from a spindle motor current sensor and $X = \{\text{feed, DOC, time, change}\}$ the same predictors. The empirical threshold based on flank wear was fixed in $L = 7.8V$. We show in Figure 8 the predictions for **smcDC**. Table 4 shows the probability that at the time $t + h$ the predicted values overcomes the threshold L .

Table 4: Evolution of the prediction using ARIMA(1,1,0) model with covariates. Response variable is $Y=smcDC$.

h	Material A			Material B		
	y_{t+h}	\hat{y}_{t+h}	$P(\hat{y}_{t+h} > L)$	y_{t+h}	\hat{y}_{t+h}	$P(\hat{y}_{t+h} > L)$
1	4.919	4.739	0.043	8.636	8.733	0.712
2	5.355	5.096	0.064	7.007	5.620	0.096
3	5.760	5.473	0.095	7.537	6.129	0.158
4	6.148	5.827	0.134	8.080	6.510	0.220
5	7.020	6.166	0.179	8.718	7.028	0.322
6	7.237	6.542	0.240	8.760	7.418	0.409
7	7.128	6.861	0.299	9.125	7.809	0.502
8	7.566	7.173	0.362	8.552	7.566	0.444
9	8.302	7.481	0.429	8.682	8.105	0.573
10	8.570	7.836	0.508	8.651	8.496	0.662

Figure 8: Forecasts of $smcDC$ using the ARIMAX(1,1,0) model: observed $smcDC$ in black, point forecasts in blue, 80% (dark gray) and 95% (light gray) prediction intervals, limit of tool replacement in red for material A (left panel) and material B (right panel).

2.3.5. Life time data for Mill Data Set

In this Section we apply lifetime data analysis techniques to the sixteen milling inserts by considering their different operating conditions (feed, material and depth of cut). One of the inserts provided no data, so it was eliminated from the analyses. As mentioned, it is considered that the cutting tool has failed when the flank wear on the milling insert exceeds a standard threshold level. Figure 9 shows the evolution of the flank wear VB along the several runs of the 15 remaining inserts. From this Figure 9 it is seen that the cutting tool is replaced after the VB signal gets large. For illustrative purposes we define the time to failure as the time from tool replacement to event $VB > 0.5$. For three inserts VB was below 0.5 throughout all their runs; in this case, the time to failure was right-censored by the total operating time. In Table 5 we give the basic information; the time to failure is reported by the variable *time*, while the variable *status* takes the value 0 for censored cases.

Figure 9: Flank wear evolution (VB) in black, a potential threshold in red and instant in which a new case is restarted (see experimental conditions in Appendix).

Table 5: Basic information of the data when the VB overcomes the threshold of 0.5mm.

case	N. runs	VB	status	time	DOC	feed	material
1	17	0.44	0	48	1.50	0.50	1
2	14	0.55	1	72	0.75	0.50	1
3	16	0.55	1	81	0.75	0.25	1
4	7	0.49	0	39	1.50	0.25	1
5	5	0.53	1	12	1.50	0.50	2
6	1	NA*	0	NA	1.50	0.25	2
7	7	0.46	0	19	0.75	0.25	2
8	6	0.62	1	12	0.75	0.50	2
9	8	0.64	1	40	1.50	0.50	1
10	9	0.53	1	45	1.50	0.25	1
11	20	0.57	1	86	0.75	0.25	1
12	14	0.58	1	67	0.75	0.50	1
13	9	0.56	1	25	0.75	0.25	2
14	8	0.60	1	18	0.75	0.50	2
15	6	0.56	1	16	1.50	0.25	2
16	6	0.62	1	9	1.50	0.50	2

*Not available (NA): Flank wear was not always measured and at times when no measurements were taken, no entry was made.

We fitted a Weibull regression model (Eq. 6) to the 15 failure data points. For this, we used the `survreg` function of the R package `survival`. The numerical output was the following:

```

survreg(formula = Surv(time, status) ~ as.factor(DOC) +
as.factor(feed) +
as.factor(material), data = mill, dist = "weibull")
              Value Std. Error      z      p
(Intercept)    4.4819    0.0682  65.72 < 2e-16
as.factor(DOC)1.5 -0.4147    0.0623  -6.65 2.9e-11
as.factor(feed)0.5 -0.2597    0.0681  -3.82 0.00014
as.factor(material)2 -1.3373    0.0666 -20.07 < 2e-16
Log(scale)      -2.2664    0.2436  -9.30 < 2e-16

Scale= 0.104
Weibull distribution
Loglik(model)= -35.3   Loglik(intercept only)= -57.2
      Chisq= 43.87 on 3 degrees of freedom, p= 1.6e-09
Number of Newton-Raphson Iterations: 12, n= 15

```

From the numerical output, it is seen that the deep of cut, the feed and the material are significant stress factors for the tool ($p < 0.05$), which tends to fail earlier for a deeper cut, larger feed, and material B. The acceleration factors (exponential transforms of minus the regression coefficients) were 1.51 (DOC), 1.30 (feed), and 3.81 (material), while the factors multiplying the failure rate were 54.6, 12.2 and 3.99×10^5 respectively. See Section 2.2 for more details about PH and AFT models.

Table 6 shows the mean residual time life (minutes) at different times t depending on the type of material and working conditions (DOC, feed). Specifically, we consider for illustration the sampling quartiles of the observed failure times, $t=17.0$, 39.0 and 57.5 minutes. We also include $t=0$ for completeness, as in this case the mean residual time reduces to the overall mean.

Table 6: Mean residual time life (MRL) at time t from Weibull distribution using Eq. 4.

Material	DOC	feed	t=0	t=17	t=39	t=57.5
1	0.75	0.25	83.89	66.97	44.97	26.55
1	1.50	0.25	55.47	38.47	16.54	1.75
1	0.75	0.50	64.77	47.77	25.78	8.26
1	1.50	0.50	42.78	25.78	4.64	0.00
2	0.75	0.25	22.05	5.12	0.00	0.00
2	1.50	0.25	14.56	0.03	0.00	0.00
2	0.75	0.50	17.00	0.87	0.00	0.00
2	1.50	0.50	11.23	0.00	0.00	0.00

The estimated mean residual time function can be used for dynamic prediction where, at each time point, the average remaining lifetime is updated. See Figure 10 in which we depict the mean-based predictions ($t=0$) as an illustration. Intervals for the mean residual time (confidence intervals) and for the particular failure time (prediction intervals) at a user-supplied level can be provided too. The estimated model also allows for the computation of future failure probabilities which take the current operation time into account. In this way, the end user may prepare her/himself to stop the production/replace the cutting tool at a certain future time when such anticipated probability is above a given level.

In order to ensure the accuracy of the prediction, model assessment must be performed. Graphical plots based on residuals are a standard device in lifetime data analysis for such a goal. The residuals can be computed by transforming the observed failure times through the model-based estimated cumulative hazard (i.e. the cumulative failure rate). If the model is appropriate, the Nelson-Aalen estimate of the cumulative hazard of such residuals should fit the line $y=x$. In Figure 11 we report such a plot for the Weibull model estimated from the milling inserts; this figure indicates a reasonable fit of the Weibull model to this dataset. In case that a strong deviation from the fitted model is detected, the user may specify an alternative AFT model for the lifetime data (e.g. lognormal, loglogistic), or may move towards a more flexible, semiparametric model such as the PH model.

Figure 10: Observed failure times (circles; red for censored data) and mean-based predictions (crosses) for milling inserts.

Figure 11: Residual plot for model assessment: Weibull model for milling inserts.

2.3.6. Computational details for TSA and LTA

The regression modelling has been performed in R software with:

- TSA: `arima` (stats package)
- QC (qcc package)
- LTA: `survreg` (survival package, AFT) and `coxph` (survival package, PH)

The problem was solved in a computer with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8550 CPU @ 1.8GHz, 16.0 GB RAM and a Windows 10 operating system.

3. Statistical models for predicting vibration level and machine probability of failure

The economic losses due to the lost of availability is, in general, one of the major sources of losses in producing companies. Also, inability of fulfilling the delivering time schedule is one of the major causes behind losses in the customers and market shares and consequently company profit, Al-Najjar (2007), (Al-Najjar & Algabroun 2018). These types of losses are strongly influenced by the performance of maintenance and its effectiveness. The accuracy of maintenance decisions when it concerns when and why to stop a producing machine or to let the production run, is essential for reducing the economic losses based on the unnecessary stoppages of the production process (Al-Najjar 2016). This issue acquires even higher importance in the companies of intensive capital investment where stoppage time is expensive, such as the cases of the PreCoM use-cases. In order to overcome this issue, PreCoM will utilize algorithms that enhance the accuracy of maintenance decisions. These algorithms are within the Smart eMDSS software platform. In this deliverable, we will present these algorithms, i.e. PreVib and ProLife, that will be used in PreCoM to support accurate maintenance decision.

The major characteristic of the maintenance adapted is to enhance maintenance decision accuracy and cost-effectiveness in order to reduce the economic losses that company suffers from. A solution that will be utilized in PreCoM to achieve this is the Smart eMaintenance Decision Support System (Smart eMDSS), which has the following characteristics:

1. It provides underlying information for more accurate, dynamic and cost-effective maintenance decisions
2. It demands more specific information; partly available in the machine/company database and partly should be gathered from the production process
3. It can be used for different objectives, for example, it can be used for more accurate maintenance decisions, identifying and prioritising problem areas, simulation for identifying the most cost-effective solution, and for following up, controlling and assessment of losses and maintenance cost-effectiveness

Smart eMDSS is a verified and commercialized software solution platform that is utilized by several Swedish companies. Smart eMDSS (see Figure 12) is consisted of 3 toolsets, which their main objectives as follow:

- mapping, analysing and improving maintenance and production processes
- identifying and prioritising problem areas and the root-causes
- assessing the losses in production time and profit
- simulation for selecting the most cost-effective solution
- following up, controlling and assessment of maintenance cost-effectiveness

In the next sections we will:

1. Describe the theoretical background behind Smart eMDSS tools and software programs that are considered for PreCoM.
2. Describe these software tools, their functions and possible applications.

Figure 12: Maintenance Decision Support System (Smart eMDSS).

3.1. A Mechanistic Model for Predicting the Vibration-level of a Machine

Vibration-based maintenance (VBM) based on the concept of total quality maintenance (TQMain) increases the chance of detecting damage, of a component/equipment at an early stage in order to act for keeping the probability of failure of machine's significant components low until a condition-based replacement is done (Al-Najjar 2000). In other words, the effective usage of VBM within TQMain enables the user to plan and perform cost-effective actions before damage on a component is initiated. When making vibration measurements, the vibration pattern given from the processing machine, provide detailed information about the machines condition. The vibration level can be measured according to different parameters, such as vibration displacement, velocity or acceleration. Each parameter has its own range of application (White 1984). When the damage is initiated, the CM parameter can give enough information about component's current condition. The hazard rate can then be kept low as long as the vibration level describing the component condition is still below the warning or replacement level. Mechanical and electrical systems in power stations, paper mills, hydraulic systems, etc. consist of many sub-systems, components and modules such as rolling element bearings, pumps, motors and gearboxes. Replacing the mechanical parts at the right time, which could be achieved by using condition-based maintenance (CBM) or age replacement at cost-optimised interval, reduces the contribution of each part to the system rate of occurrence of failures (ROCOF) and therefore reduces the ROCOF itself (Sherwin 2000).

If we can assess the condition of the machine's significant components accurately, we can prolong the mean effective life length of the components, Al-Najjar (2000). Assessing the component's condition is done effectively, i.e. with high certainty, through considering both the deterministic and probabilistic approaches simultaneously for modelling the deterioration process. Issues related to machine function, failures analysis and diagnostics are example of the deterministic approach. While modelling the time to maintenance action and the probability of failure of the component when damage is detected are examples of the probabilistic approach. When a potential failure (damage under development) of a significant component is detected, predicting the value of the CM parameter,

e.g. vibration level, during the interval until the next measurement or planned stoppage, accurately, would enhance the effectiveness of maintenance decision-making process.

3.1.1. Life Time of a Mechanical Component

In general, the life of a component consists of three different phases: no defect, defect initiation and development (potential failure), and imminent failure. The second phase represents more than half the total usable life of a component/equipment, Al-Najjar (2000). Technically, the probability that a component will fail depends on its past history, current status and its operating and environmental conditions during the near future. The CM parameter level is usually considered stationary during the interval prior to the initiation of damage and is fluctuating about its mean value (x_0). However, as illustrated in Figure 13, after damage initiation the CM parameter value, i.e. $x(t)$, may be assumed increasing (exponentially) in operating time, see Herraty (1993) and Al-Najjar (1990 and 1997) and Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004).

Figure 13: The mean level x_0 and potential failure level, x_p of a CM parameter.

A potential failure can be defined as an identifiable physical condition, which indicates that damage is initiated and under development, and an actual failure may occur eventually if no relevant maintenance action is taken. A part from the case where changes in the component condition have not been detected at an early stage, the component has no chance to fail when there is no damage initiated and as long as the levels of relevant CM parameters are still below the replacement level. Consequently, the probability of failure may be assumed to be very low (approximately zero) during this interval. Denote the level at which a potential failure is considered initiated by x_p , so that $x_0 \ll x_p$, see Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004).

Observations have shown that it is often difficult to tell for certain that the second phase has begun, especially when the number of CM measurements, e.g. vibration, is very small. In many cases, the cumulative sum (CUSUM) chart of the condition measurements is a better indicator of a potential failure than the measurement itself, see Al-Najjar (1990 and 1997). This is because of the random fluctuating of the condition, e.g. vibration measurements, which may occur according to some uncontrolled disturbing factors independent of component's condition. The CUSUM chart as well as other control charts need to manage false alarms, so that the risk of having it is small. At the same time a control chart should be sensitive, in manner of indicating change(s) in the process as soon as possible after its occurrence. The CUSUM chart is obtained by plotting the sum of deviations from a target value (predetermined level), see for example Bergman and Klefsjö (1995).

Once the potential failure of the CM parameter level is assessed, exceeding this level insures the initiation of a potential failure and indicates the beginning of the wear-out interval, see Al-Najjar (1997). In this interval, $x(t)$ may be assumed to be a non-decreasing function. Potential failure level

should be assessed for each case because it varies even for identical components. At each measurement, after a potential failure is detected, the time needed by a component to approach the replacement (failure) level is a random variable. Based on the component deterioration rate and the predicted CM parameter level during the near future it is possible to assess the moment of replacement graphically, Al-Najjar (1997 and 2003). But, a probabilistic model (discussed later) is necessary for assessing the component's residual time and for describing the risk of failures or the dispersion (uncertainty) in the predicted CM parameter level after each measurement to enhance the decision making process.

The time to the initiation of a potential failure is a random variable as well due to the randomness of the time variant factors influencing the component condition. Denote by the random variable ζ_p the time to a potential failure and denote the wear out phase by ζ_w . Then the random time to failure (or approximately to just before failure replacement) is;

$$\zeta = \zeta_p + \zeta_w$$

But, as long as it is possible to detect the potential failures in significant mechanical components using a suitable CM parameter, e.g. vibration, with a good certainty, where its probability of failure during ζ_p is very small, then we need only to consider the risk of failure during the wear-out phase, i.e. during ζ_w , see Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004).

3.1.2. *Theoretical description - A mechanistic model to predict the vibration level*

There are many commercial systems for monitoring the condition of significant components and their effectiveness usually differs one from another, see Al-Najjar (1997 and 2001). For instance, using an efficient vibration monitoring system and as long as the relevant vibration frequencies or bands for monitoring the state of a significant component are identified, the detection of damage can be done with very high probability. As long as the monitored vibration level is fluctuating around its mean level, measurements can be considered as normally distributed, which implies that there is no damage initiated. An alarm should be released as soon as the level of the selected vibration frequency or band significantly deviates from x_0 , see Figure 13. More investigation is required to make sure that it is not a false warning, which is possible due to the randomness in the vibration signals and existence of noise. Also, it is possible to wait until the measured vibration level exceeds the first alarm level (x_p) confirming that the damage is under development. When the monitored vibration level is increasing or significantly high, maintenance engineers need then, at each measuring moment, to decide whether or not it is urgent to perform the required maintenance action. This is why it is very important to get as much as possible information to make the decision-making process easier and cost-effective. For example, for any production or maintenance manager it will be much easier to decide whether to proceed running the machine or stop it if the following information is given, see Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004):

- Past data such as vibration trend describing the component's behaviour and current condition that includes diagnosis of damage causes, development mechanisms and possible failure modes, which are usually available when implementing condition-based maintenance (CBM).
- Predicted CM parameter value during the period following the recent measurement and until the next planned CM parameter measurement or next planned stoppage.
- Assessment of the probability of failure of the significant component during the same period.
- Assessment of the residual life of the significant component.

- Economic justification of whether the maintenance action should be done now or at the next convenient moment.

In order to complete the set of information needed for decision-making (i.e. item two in the previous list) a model was developed for predicting the CM parameter level, e.g. vibration level, during the period until the time point for next measuring, see Al-Najjar (2001). The model is illustrated by Eq. 1. Y is the dependent variable representing the predicted value of the CM parameter. It is function of three independent variables (X , Z and T) and three parameters (a , b and c). For $i = 1, 2 \dots n$, and i is the number of measuring opportunities after damage initiation, see Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004).

$$Y_{i+1} = X_i + a * \text{Exp}(b_i * T_{i+1} * Z_i^{c_i}) + E_i \quad (7)$$

Where

- Y_{i+1} The predicted value of the CM level at the next planned measuring time.
 T_{i+1} The elapsed time since the damage is initiated and its development is detected.
 X_i The current CM level.
 Z_i The deterioration factor, a function of the current and anticipated load and previous deterioration rate. ($Z = dx' * Lf/Lc$)
 a Is the gradient (slope) by which the value of the CM parameter varied since it started to deviate from its normal state x_0 due to initiation of damage until detecting it at x_p .
 b_i & c_i Non-linear model's constants.
 E_i The model error, which is assumed to be identical, independent and normally distributed with zero mean and constant variance, $N(0, \sigma)$.

The prediction of the close future vibration levels is based on several essential factors in the deterioration process and when a significant vibration level is approached according to the development of damage. Although the uses the following essential factors;

1. Previous vibration measurement,
2. Current condition,
3. Previous and future operating conditions, such as loading, but the major focus is given on the recent vibration measurements out of the whole vibration history to avoid under- or overestimation of the vibration level.

In the model, previous vibration measurements that are usually used for illustrating the trend of vibration level development are utilised for;

1. Identifying the interval when damage is initiated which is very important for developing a potential failure
2. Identifying the gradient in the damage development.

3.2. Total-Time-on-Test (TTT) Plots for Assessing Probability of Failure and Residual Time

It is usually preferred to base improvements of CM techniques on the techniques' past data. This is because each CM system and its application may be considered unique. Disturbing factors generated at the monitored equipment/component and surroundings that influence CM measurements usually lead to false signals (Al-Najjar 2016). These are the worst enemy of maintenance engineers, those who attempt to achieve accurate interpretation of CM, e.g. vibration measurements. These disturbances in many cases lead to over- (or under-) estimation of the equipment condition. The

economic losses that arise due to the false signals are significant especially when the downtime cost is high (Al-Najjar 2016).

TTT-plots for equipment/components are usually obtained from failure data, i.e. machine past failure data or data has been collected during an experiment. Documented history of the condition-based replacements and failures of the equipment/component in question are used for the purpose of application examples. This graphical method is related to Total Time on Test, TTT-plot, as introduced by Barlow (1975). In the application example, a bearing is considered as rolling element bearing and the component is the smallest part in the machine and has a particular function such as bearing. When using CBM, the most important data, which are needed to avoid failures, are:

- The predetermined level of the measured CM parameter (variable), such as vibration, at which a planned replacement should be performed.
- CM measurement trend. The trend of the measurements of a CM parameter is ordinarily used to describe changes in the state of a mechanical component, e.g. rolling element bearing.

3.2.1. Theoretical description

In this section, the theoretical background behind the development of the models for assessing the probability of failure of a significant component and the residual life using past data from the machine and component in question is introduced.

A Failure Model

A failure is defined in British Standard, Glossary of Terms used in Terotechnology, BS 3811:1993 as: "The termination of the ability of an item to perform its required function" and it is defined by Nowlan (1978), Reliability Centred-Maintenance (RCM), as: "An unsatisfactory condition". Al-Najjar (2006) defines it as a termination of a component's ability, to perform its required function, which can be defined on basis of the machine function, capability, availability, production rate, production cost, product quality, and/or personnel/machine safety. In most cases it is possible to carry out replacements just before failure if an efficient CBM system based on a reliable CM technique is adopted. The failure of a machine is assumed to be announced as soon as an unsatisfactory condition is approached, i.e. when the value of the CM parameter (or parameters) exceeds a predetermined level. This level would be defined on the basis of one or more of the elements deciding whether the equipment/component is considered in a failure situation or not such as equipment function, product quality, production cost, etc. (Al-Najjar 2012). Monitoring the condition of equipment/component can be carried out either through observing one CM parameter or a set of parameters. For these CM parameters, it is always possible to state predetermined, i.e. maximal acceptable, levels.

The failure data needed in statistical analysis is not always available because the companies try to perform replacement before failure (even if this leads to over-maintaining) due to the failure consequential cost. Therefore, special experiments are often required to obtain the required data. These experiments are often; expensive, deviate from reality appreciably and are not always easy to conduct. For the given reasons, condition-based replacement data will be considered to obtain TTT-plots as an aid to assess a bearing's condition. Bearing's history will be utilised to perform this task. In this context condition-based replacements mean, all the data that is related to the replacements done depending on the analysis and assessments of the measurements collected by the CM system. Suppose that given n observations t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n from a particular life distribution $F(\cdot)$. Let these observations be ordered due to their sizes, i.e. $t_1 \leq t_2 \leq \dots \leq t_n$. Thus t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n represents n times to failure in increasing order. Let T_i denote the total time generated in ages less or equal to t_i , i.e. $T_i = nt_i$, and generally

$$T_i = \sum_{j=1}^i (n-j+1)(t_j - t_{j-1}) \quad (8)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, n$ where $t_0 = 0$. Also, let $u_i = T_i/T_n$. The application of TTT-plots is explained in Example 1.

Example 1

Assume that 8 components are observed until failures, their times to failure, ζ_1, \dots, ζ_8 , and the calculated quantities are shown in Table 7. The TTT-plot is obtained by plotting u_i versus i/n , as shown in Figure 14. U_i is the ratio of the total time on test until the i -th unit fails, T_i , and the total time on test until all units fail, T_n . The TTT-plot gives a dimensionless view representing times to failure of the tested components. The deviation of the plot from the diagonal provides information about the deviation of the plotted data (life distribution) from the exponential distribution. Also, it is a useful tool for identifying life length models as shown by Bergman (1977).

Table 7: Failure times and calculated quantities of the TTT-plot show in Figure 12.

i	ζ_i	T_i	u_i	i/n
1	8.7	69.6	0.267	0.125
2	11.6	89.9	0.345	0.250
3	21.3	148.1	0.568	0.375
4	26.1	172.1	0.660	0.500
5	37.4	217.3	0.834	0.625
6	38.2	219.7	0.843	0.750
7	49.8	242.9	0.930	0.875
8	67.5	260.6	1.000	1.000

In other words, the TTT-plot is considered as an estimation of the TTT-transform of the underlying distribution of the observed data, Bergman and Klefsjö (1995). If the hazard rate is an increasing function of the component age, then the TTT-plot approaches a concave curve for a large number of observations, Figure 14. Conversely, it approaches a convex curve if the hazard rate is decreasing. But, the plot of data from a distribution, in which the hazard rate is decreasing at first and increasing later, has at first a convex curve and later a concave curve.

Figure 14: TTT-plot of the data shown in Table 7.

3.2.2. Vibration-based Maintenance and TTT-PLOTS

In general, damaged components generate specific frequencies. These frequencies can be identified and used to assess component/equipment condition. Using vibration measurements to detect faults in shafts and couplings such as imbalance, bending and misalignment, the overall Root Mean Square (RMS) vibration level is a reliable measure to assess the state of the shaft and coupling, Al-Najjar (1997) and the references cited there. But, this measure is relatively insensitive to the changes in the state of bearings or gears. Due to the low energy included in the vibration frequencies generated by bearing or (gear wheel) damage, these frequencies have very little (or no) effect on the overall RMS vibration level.

In general, bearing damage cannot always be limited to only one part of a bearing such as inner or outer race, rolling elements or cage after a period of damage initiation. If damage is started at one part, e.g. the inner or the outer race, it probably spreads gradually to the other parts. Thus, the evaluation of the bearing condition would not be reliable if it was based on monitoring damage vibration frequency of only one part of the bearing. The total vibration energy generated by bearing damage may be a fair measure of bearing deterioration. Thus, the RMS mm/s of the essential frequency/frequencies generated by bearing damage is suggested as a measure of the bearing's condition, call it Bearing Defect Vibration Energy (BDVE). The essential frequencies are defined as; bearing damage frequencies and their multiples, which exceed a predetermined level, Figure 14. This level can be decided based on the component/equipment vibration history and the noise-to-signal ratio. It is assumed that the condition of a bearing can be evaluated from the previous measurements and current value of BDVE. Call the value of a CM parameter, such as BDVE, a parameter value and denote it by $x(t)$ at age t . When using vibration-based maintenance (VBM), the replacement is often performed as soon as the predetermined level is approached or exceeded. Thus, according to the traditional failure definition, not enough failure data are available at the industries implementing VBM. The residual mean effective life of a bearing can be assessed by, e.g. using the graphical method suggested by Al-Najjar (1996 II).

Total Time on Test may be understood as Total Time in Operation because we are using condition-based replacement (and failure if existent) data instead of just failure or test data. Suppose that the parameter values, e.g. the monitored vibration levels of n identical bearings, at different locations in the machine but of identical operating conditions, are monitored until respective replacement times or at unplanned-but-before-failure replacements (UPBFR), $\tau_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where no failures are experienced. UPBFRs are performed at unplanned occasions but before failure stoppages in order to prevent the occurrence of imminent failures. This situation arises because of a sudden increment in the measured variable(s), e.g. the vibration level, due to one or more damage causes, which were not detected at an early stage.

Define $x_j = \sup x_j(t), t$. That is x_j is the largest value that the monitoring parameter acquired during the monitoring time, e.g. running time (age) t , where $t \leq \tau_j$. Order the indices so that $x(i)$ corresponds to that x_j which is the i th in size. Then, the ordered indices are $x_{(1)} x_{(2)} \dots x_{(n)}$. Define $S_j(x)$ as the total time on test generated by the j th bearing before its parameter value exceeds the level $x_{(j)}$ for the first time, i.e.

$$S_j(x) = \inf \{t; x_j(t) \geq x_{(j)}\}$$

Let $S(x) = S_j(x)$

Define $T_i = S(x_{(i)})$, which is the total time accumulated by all bearings while their parameter values are less than or equal to $x_{(i)}, i=1, \dots, n$. The plot of the Total Time on Test can then be obtained in the usual way, i.e. plot of $u_i = T_i/T_n$ against i/n . The ratio i/n is actually an estimation of the probability that the failure occurs if no planned replacement or UPBFR is done, where i is the number of planned

(condition-based) and UPBFRs done before their parameter value exceeds the level $x_{(i)}$ for the first time. Letter n is the total number of the bearings under consideration and T_n/n is an estimate of the expected time to a planned replacement or UPBFR. The cost incurred by an unplanned-but-before-failure replacement is considered to be approximately equal to the cost incurred by a failure of the same component/equipment. Denote by c_1 and c_2 the cost incurred by a planned action and an additional cost, which is suffered only at failure/UPBFR respectively. The costs c_1 and c_2 are considered independent of maintenance policy. Denote by $T_{i_0, \pi}$ the time to planned replacement at the index i_0 and when using maintenance policy π .

Thus, the estimate of the minimum long run average cost per unit time (C_π) when technique π is used can be written (The index i_0 minimising C_π can be estimated graphically) see Al-Najjar (1999);

$$C = \frac{c_1 + c_2 \frac{i_0, \pi}{n}}{\frac{i}{n} T_{i_0, \pi}}$$

4. Maintenance Decision Support System (Smart eMDSS) using TTT-plots and Mechanistic model

When applying condition-based maintenance (CBM), usually the level of the condition monitoring (CM) parameter is considered significant when its value exceeds a particular level, e.g. warning level (Al-Najjar 2016). At that significant level, it is necessary to gather more information concerning the component/equipment in question before making any decision (Al-Najjar 2012). In other words, the information required should be wider than trend data and current situation of that component. This is why Smart eMDSS offers additional information, i.e;

- a) Predicted vibration level at next near future, such as the moment of the next planned measurement or stoppage.
- b) At the same time, it is also necessary to assess the residual time especially when production manager would like to assure smooth running of the production process until the production is delivered according to the schedule.
- c) In some cases, the probability of failure based on previous experience of the same component/equipment would be helpful to clarify the situation more.

All these measures in addition to the usually available measures, such as trend data and current condition will increase the accuracy of the maintenance decision and enhance its cost-effectiveness.

Detecting any deviation in the condition of a component/equipment increases the need for identifying all possible ways of solutions/actions. In many cases these alternative actions/solutions are all technically suitable but not necessarily equally cost-effective. Toolset 2 (see Figure 12) provides the possibility of simulating all relevant alternative actions in order to select the most cost-effective. This tool will not be applied in PreCoM.

In toolsets 3 (see Figure 12), we will consider only MainSave to follow up, control and assess the losses in production and profit, through providing the possibility to:

- a) assess the losses in production time.
- b) identify and prioritise problem areas and basic causes behind losses in the production time
- c) assess cost-effectiveness of maintenance through; identifying and assessment of maintenance direct cost, saving, investments and results (maintenance losses or profit), for more details see D8.6.

4.1. Accurate Maintenance Decision Toolset: PreVib and ProLife

In the following sections, two tools in their software format will be introduced. The tools aim to enhance the accuracy of maintenance decisions.

First tool is PreVib, a mechanistic model for predicting the vibration level, when using vibration-based maintenance (VBM). Its aim is to detect significant deviations in the condition of a component at an early stage in order to act for keeping the probability of failure of machine/significant component low until a condition-based replacement is done, Al-Najjar (2000).

The second tool is ProLife, a probabilistic approach. It is for assessing the probability of failure of a component/equipment.

The second tool is also used to assess the residual lifetime of a component/equipment when its condition monitoring level, e.g. vibration level is significantly high.

The theoretical development of these tools is based on Total Quality Maintenance (TQMain) concept. This is why it is necessary that before introducing these methods the concept of Total Quality

Maintenance (TQMain) will be introduced briefly in order to make the reader more acquainted with the terminology used.

Total quality maintenance (TQMain) is a philosophy that enables the user to maintain and improve continuously the technical and economic effectiveness of process elements through maintaining the quality of all relevant elements involved in a production process. Thus, TQMain's role is for monitoring and controlling deviations in a process condition and product quality, and for detecting failure causes and potential failures in order to interfere when it is possible to arrest or reduce machine deterioration rate before the product characteristics are intolerably affected and to perform the required action to restore the machine/process or a particular part of it to good as new. All these should be performed at a continuously reducing cost per unit of good quality product. (Al-Najjar, 1996 I and 2007)

4.2. Software design and test of mechanistic model

4.2.1. Data definition and gathering

To test the new Smart eMDSS software/tool PreVib, the same data was used that have been gathered from a Swedish paper mill and published in Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004). This vibration data was collected during a case study about a spherical roller bearing installed at the paper mill machine. The object for measurement was bearing 23052cc/SKF (but in Figure 15 is given the name Asset XYZ009, Bearing XYZ). The data used in the test of PreVib is presented in Table 8. The data that are relevant for testing the model are; time point (calendar time) of measurements and the vibration level (mm/sec) at each of the measuring moment. The range of data represents the vibration level at the time when the bearing was installed until it was replaced. The reason for using the data from the published paper was to test whether the software of the tool PreVib would achieve the same or similar results as those achieved in Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004).

The measurements that have been considered are whose values indicate a significant change in the condition of the component is undergoing. In other words, the service of PreVib is not necessary to be used if the measurement of vibration level value still (in the phase 1) fluctuates about x_o , i.e. no damage is initiated. It may take some time (measurements) until it is evident that damage is initiated and under development, i.e. entered phase 2. The vibration level is considered significant (damage initiated and under development) when its value starts to exceed x_p Figure 15 PreVib uses just few of the vibration level measurements from phase 1 and all the measurements that lie above, x_p until the level of replacement. Therefore, before using PreVib it is necessary to have clear predetermined levels (x_o & x_p) and replacement level (x_r).

In the previous method, the non-linear model's constants b and c (see Eq. 7), and variables Z (the deterioration factor) and a (the gradient, slope, of deviation from normal state x_o due to damage initiation until detecting it at x_p) were estimated by means of tools such as mathematical software MatLab. PreVib integrates all these inputs such as variables and algorithms, so that a prediction of a future prediction level can be done in one platform.

Table 8: Asset vibration measurements, data from Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004).

asset_id	gmt_measurement	vibration_level
9	2007-01-26	0.84
9	2007-03-23	0.84
9	2007-05-29	0.95
9	2007-08-11	1.15
9	2007-08-12	1.72
9	2007-08-13	2.22
9	2007-08-14	2.69
9	2007-08-15	3.15
9	2007-08-16	3.75
9	2007-08-17	3.85

Note: the unit for vibration level is mm/s. The table is reconstructed according to MIMOSA.

4.2.2. Software development and test

PreVib is based on theoretical model expressed in Eq. 7 and is one of the tools included by the toolset for enhancing maintenance decisions/ Smart eMDSS. For easy use of the model and in order to achieve reliable results, new software based on PreVib model was developed at the department of Terotechnology, Växjö University. The three predetermined levels (phases) of a component life, i.e. x_o , x_p and replacement level are also included in this dataset. The results of the conducted test are shown in Figure 15. The user interface can be divided into two halves: left half representing input data for prediction and right half representing the result in form of a graph. When a prediction is to be made, i.e. when the vibration level acquires a significant level, firstly one need to specify the segment (machine), asset (component, in this case a rolling element bearing), the prediction time period and the ratio between near future load and present load, followed by load-button click which uploads the data from a database (MIMOSA). In the input box for prediction time period one has to specify the desired future prediction time point in days. The user interface then receives the measure time point, vibration level data and the three levels (phases) of component life. This is required input for making the prediction of the vibration level when the predict-button is clicked for determining the value of the predict vibration level and plot it on the diagram on the right hand side of the user interface. By analogy, the same thing can be repeated any time the user need to predict the vibration level.

The right half of the user interface presents a graph containing two plots, the blue representing the actual vibration level data and the red showing the predicted vibration at next measurement time. Y-axis is the vibration level in mm/sec and x-axis is the calendar time for measurements and predictions. The graph has also three dashed lines representing the three different levels of life of a mechanical component i.e. mean vibration level (x_o), potential failure level (x_p) and replacement level. These levels are determined and set based on data from identical components and is automatically retrieved when component data is uploaded. In this case, mean vibration level is estimated to 0.95 mm/sec, the potential failure level at which the damage initiation is confirmed is estimated to 1.5 mm/sec and finally the replacement level is estimated at the vibration level of 3.85 mm/sec. The lowest dashed line represents the mean (normal) vibration level (x_o), around which the CM parameter level value fluctuates most of its life, see Figure 15 right half. One can see that the curve increases exponentially after the damage initiation has been confirmed (the point in the graph with a circle), which is an expected behaviour, see Herraty (1993) and Al-Najjar (1990 and 1997) and Al-Najjar and Alsyouf (2004).

Some of the initial measurements are not shown in the graph, but they have been considered when estimating model's constants b and c . The first prediction, as evident, is done after confirming damage initiation. To be able to predict future vibration level one need at least three measurements. It has to be mentioned that first two predictions are special cases, where we use measurements below the potential failure level to assess model's parameters b and c . The reason for that is that we want to predict future state as soon as we have confirmed the initiation of damage, instead of waiting for at least three measurements passed potential failure level. Waiting could also cause uncertainty in the maintenance decisions. Also, because deterioration process is a stochastic process, vibration level can be changed randomly in time. Therefore, some of the level values may acquire higher level than it should, i.e. exceeds x_p , which it may be irrelevant to the severity of the deterioration.

(a) results from prediction of vibration tool

(b) Results dashboard

Figure 15: PreVib tool (a) results from prediction of vibration tool (b) Results dashboard.

The first prediction of the vibration level should be done as soon as its value exceeds or close to x_p , because as long it fluctuates around x_o it means there is no damage is initiated and thereby there is no need for predicting future level. This is why we need some of the measurements that have been considered part of phase of the component life. For each following prediction we use all data up to measurement point for instance; prediction is done at calendar time 2007-08-14: 00.00.00, predicting the vibration level for 2007-08-15: 00.00.00 i.e. prediction time period equals one day. All data up to 2007-08-14: 00.00.00 is used for estimating model's parameters (b and c) and thus predicted vibration level itself. Exactly one day after, the actual vibration level is registered and this procedure follows until the time for replacement of the component (a rolling element bearing). By eyeballing the graph in Figure 15, we can see that the curve of the predicted values (red curve) is adjusted according to the actual values of the vibration level and can more or less be fitted into the same curve, which confirms the accuracy of the predicted values compared to actual.

4.2.3. *Results and Conclusions*

The main result is development and verification of PreVib software as a tool for predicting the vibration level in the near future. PreVib test showed similar but not exact results as in the previous tests shown in see Al-Najjar and Alsyuf (2004). One of the reasons behind this is the identification of the time point when the first prediction is done. In previous test, the first prediction of vibration level was done on the third actual measurement above the potential failure level. This due to the fact, that at least three measurements are required to make the first prediction. In the test of PreVib software, as discussed earlier, the first prediction was done at an earlier stage because measurements below potential failure were considered. This is important from the practical point of view, i.e. to avoid sudden and rapid increment of the vibration level. On the other hand, the curve representing the damage development shown in Figure 15 is not affected by the measurements belongs to the phase 1. Another result is that the software has inbuilt algorithm that takes care of estimation of model's parameters. Thus, the user of PreVib software tool does not need to perform any regression analysis on model's non-linear constants, Model development above.

Predicting the CM parameter level at the next planned measuring time or next planned stoppage reduces the risk of an unexpected deviation in the condition of the significant components, such as rolling element bearings. This means that the probability of failure of a significant component such as a rolling element bearing can be kept very low (close to zero) until damage is initiated, given that damage can be detected at an early stage through using an efficient CM system, e.g. vibration. Furthermore, component replacement could be performed at the most appropriate time. The main conclusion is that better data coverage and quality reduces the uncertainty in the predicted value of the vibration level used to describe the condition of a significant component especially when the deviation in its life length is mostly related to the operating conditions. This would reduce the number and duration of planned and unplanned stoppage that has a direct impact on the company's productivity, and hence, its competitiveness.

Monitored vibration level is usually fluctuating around mean level x_o , but the vibration monitoring equipment may show measured levels that are significantly deviating from x_o . An investigation should be done in order to secure if damage is initiated or if it was a false alarm due to some other disturbing factors such as operating environment. If the component is replaced as soon as the vibration exceeds the first alarm level (x_p), there is a risk that the replacement is done too early and remaining effective life of a component is not utilized. For enhancement of cost-effective maintenance, a maintenance technician needs, at each prediction time point, to decide whether to perform or to wait with the required maintenance action. By means of probabilistic approach one could model the time to maintenance action and thereby optimize the life and costs related to the

significant component in question. The theory presented in this paragraph, strongly advocates considering both mechanistic (PreVib) and probabilistic (ProLife) when modelling time to maintenance action. Next paragraph will present the second tool i.e. probability of failure and residual life time (ProLife).

PreVib software uses complete data set when predicting the future vibration level. This influences the slope of the curve, and may consequently influence the maintenance decision. Future research could be investigating the behaviour of the slope when only considering data above potential failure level, when predicting vibration level at next planned CM parameter measurement or next planned stoppage. By doing that the slope of the curve will be only influenced by data after damage initiation has been confirmed. Additionally, to see other effects such as, if more predicted vibration levels will lie slightly above the actual vibration levels compared to current results, in order to strengthen the accuracy of maintenance decisions.

4.3. Software design and test of TTT-plots

4.3.1. Data definition and gathering

To test the above mentioned model ProLife (for assessing the Probability of Failure and Residual Lifetime), data from Al-Najjar (2003) were used. These data represents lifetimes of several identical components, i.e. from installation to replacement. The data used for this test are presented in Table 9 & Table 10. Table 9 gives detailed information about installation and removal (replacement) of each bearing. Data relevant for testing the model are the number of tested assets (nine) and their respective lifetimes, which is retrieved from Table 9. We can see from Table 3 that the last component has not been replaced yet and it was in operation, this is why there is no removal date data in the table.

Table 9: Asset data.

asset_id	segment_id	gmt_installed	gmt_removed
1	1	2007-01-01 08:00:00	2007-01-10 00:48:00
2	1	2007-01-10 00:48:00	2007-01-21 15:12:00
3	1	2007-01-21 15:12:00	2007-02-11 22:24:00
4	1	2007-02-11 22:24:00	2007-03-10 00:48:00
5	1	2007-03-10 00:48:00	2007-04-16 10:24:00
6	1	2007-04-16 10:24:00	2007-05-24 15:12:00
7	1	2007-05-24 15:12:00	2007-07-13 10:24:00
8	1	2007-07-13 10:24:00	2007-09-18 22:24:00
9	1	2008-08-01 08:00:00	

4.3.2. Software development and test

Software for applying ProLife was developed at the department of Terotechnology, Växjö University (now Linnaeus University) for providing the tools included by the toolset 1. This software tool is supplementary to PreVib for enhancing the accuracy in maintenance decisions. By using these tools side by side, the accuracy in decisions will increase. On the other hand ProLife could be used independently as well as PreVib. From Table 9, the data of the first 8 components are historical data and were used for assessing the probability of failure and residual lifetime (ProLife) of component nine. The object for measurement shown in Figure 16, i.e. XYZ009 Bearing XYZ represents component nine in Table 9. Notice that this object is not the same as used for testing PreVib in Figure 15.

Table 10: Assets (Bearings).

asset_id	as_type_code	user_tag_ident
1	1	XYZ001
2	1	XYZ002
3	1	XYZ003
4	1	XYZ004
5	1	XYZ005
6	1	XYZ006
7	1	XYZ007
8	1	XYZ008
9	1	XYZ009

Data given in Table 9 were used to test ProLife software tool and the results of conducted test are presented in Figure 16. As for PreVib and ProLife user interface is divided into two halves: left half representing input data for assessment and analysis, and right half showing the result in form of a plot (graph). When an assessment of probability of failure and residual lifetime is to be performed, we need to specify the segment (machine) and asset (component, a rolling element bearing in this case) followed by assess-button click which will assess the probability of failure and residual lifetime of the component nine in Table 9. Subsequently the program uploads the table of lifetime distributions from a database (MIMOSA) and presents the graph on the right half of the user interface. The y-axis in the graph shows the proportion of the average exhausted lifetime and the x-axis shows the probability of failure for the analysed component. The cross-air pointer in the graph shows the current state of the analysed component. Assessment time point is shown above the graph in Figure 16.

If a new assessment is performed after the current assessment time point, then consequently the cross-air pointer will move forward on the curve. Each point on the graph represents each and one of the component lifetimes in relation to each other. In this test we are about to analyse a component (component nine in Table 9), that was installed 2008-08-01 08:00:00 and the date of assessment was 2008-09-13 13:30:50. In other words the lifetime of the component had reached approximately 1.5 months. By eye-balling the lifetime distributions table in Figure 16, one can see the lowest lifetime was 8.7 days and highest was 67.5 days. Based on these margins and other components lifetime distributions, the assessment of probability of failure and residual lifetime for component nine was performed. Also, the data coverage quality has a strong impact on the accuracy of the assessment according to presented theory.

At assessment time point (2008-09-13 13:30:50) the result was following: probability of failure of the component was approximately 56% and its residual lifetime barely 7 days. From the graph, we can also read that approximate exhausted life time is 80%. By means of this information, the maintenance engineer could draw the conclusion that immediate actions are to be undertaken. But, in order to make an accurate and cost-effective decision he/she should also consider the PreVib tool to get as much information about the component in question if vibration monitoring is used for that component. From these tools, the maintenance engineer can model the optimum time, i.e. the most cost-effective time, for any maintenance action, such as replacement having in mind aspects such as costs, time frame and time needed for replacement, component in stock etc. The graph in Figure 16 approaches a concave curve, which is according to theory presented in this report, when the hazard rate is an increasing function of the component age.

Figure 16: Assessment of Probability of Failure and Residual Lifetime (ProLife).

4.3.3. Results and Conclusions

When using the past history of, e.g. a large number of identical rolling element bearings, it becomes easier to decide whether an increment in the vibration level is serious or not. Monitoring ProLife (GTTT-plot), the probability of failure of a damaged bearing at any time $t > 0$ can be assessed, which can be used in addition to the vibration current value and its historical trend to reliably illustrate bearing state. Monitoring the mean effective life of identical bearings and their probability density function is useful to detect dramatic changes in the distribution of the time to failure/replacement, which is an indication of whether there are deviations in the quality of these bearings and in their operating/environmental conditions.

When using a periodic measurement system for monitoring vibration, the time between measurements is almost always considered constant. It is usually assessed based on the maintenance staff's experience. But, using GTTT-plot, maintenance engineers can in advance predict the probability of replacement/failure of the bearing during the period to the next proposed measurement opportunity or planned stoppage, which yields a reliable planning of measurements. Consequently, an economic saving can be achieved. When the predicted probability of replacement/failure is low fewer measurements are needed, but when it is high, the risk of failure can be reduced by more frequent readings. The probability of replacement/failure (and the residual time) of a bearing (or any mechanical component) can then be assessed independent of the technique being used for monitoring the condition of a bearing whether it is vibration, SPM, acoustic emission or bearing age.

The main result is development and verification of software tool ProLife for assessing the failure probability and remaining lifetime of a component. ProLife was based on theoretical model given in Eq. 8, see above, and is as well as PreVib a tool that belongs to the toolset 1. The test of ProLife shows very similar results as presented in the theory and shown in Figure 16. The new software tool ProLife has made the assessment faster and more flexible than the old plotting techniques introduced in Al-Najjar (2003). The program uploads the data from MIMOSA database and creates the plot and displays all relevant information that this tool shall provide. Additionally, ProLife can be used side by

side with PreVib (if vibration monitoring technology is used) to assess component condition and determine coming maintenance actions cost-effectively. The major benefit of using this toolset is among other things to help the user in making a cost-effective decision.

5. Demo-companies in PreCoM

The methodology of TSA and LTA has proved to be useful for a proof of concept with characteristics analogous to that of the use cases. As observed in the following scheme, the first phase of the procedure requires data processing to move on to a modelling phase (estimation), in which interesting features of the procedure can be discovered (such as significant predictors), and finally to a prediction phase (time until the vibration overcomes a threshold) that can help make predictive recommendations in future deliverables.

These inputs are as follow (for more information about input parameters, please refer to D3.1):

1. The installation and removal time of components/equipment, to identify history machines/components.
2. IDs for the company, machine, critical component and other related components.
3. Component specifications.
4. Manufacturer recommendations concerning the maximum allowable level of vibration for the machine and component, if available.
5. Measurements arrangement, which includes time and location of sensor measurements.
6. Levels of normal vibration (when no damage is initiated), potential failure (when damage is initiated and under development) and replacement (the maximum allowable vibration level according to ISO norms and experience). These three levels determine when the machine/component is in a normal condition, needs more close observation and needs replacement, respectively.

Figure 17. Scheme that relates the methodology and variables to be predicted.

The output information (following the scheme shown above) will be:

1. Point and interval prediction of the variable of interest.
2. The probability that the predicted values overcomes a specified threshold.
3. The mean residual lifetime of the targeted component.

The three use cases in PreCoM, the machines of interest and the corresponding critical components will be reviewed in this section.

5.1. Use case 1: Sakana - Solaruce

PreCoM project will focus on the machining of wind turbine parts. We selected this industry given its low volume production, where the manufactured products are of high added value. In this industry, the condition of the machine tool can meaningfully affect both the quality of the machined work piece and the productivity of the machine.

SAKANA, specializes in machining wind turbine parts, with experience in milling and drilling tools. And, SORALUCE is a machine tool builder oriented towards milling solutions.

Figure 18 shows the FXR milling machine (SORALUCE's machine) installed in Sakana. It is almost exclusively dedicated to the manufacturing of hubs of the wind turbine. The hub is a complicated work piece that requires high precision machining in the boring/drilling/perforating operations and high power and cutting speed capability in the rest of the operations (see Figure 19). The machining operations consist of many different milling operations: face milling, profiling, back facing, drilling, shoulder milling, and boring. The required cutting tools depend on the operation carried out every time.

Figure 18: Soraluce FXR milling- boring machine installed in SAKANA

Figure 19: Machining operations in a hub.

The most repetitive operations in the hub machining are drilling operations where many deep milling operations must be carried out with the same cutting tool (see D7.1 for further details). However, tool wear can be very expensive to measure or unfeasible in practice, so indirect indicators such as

CM parameters (such as vibration in a critical component) can be very useful. This section analyses the tool when it is working (load data during machining/working conditions) to identify its behaviour in a repetitive process.

The Soralue FXR is a floor-type milling-boring centre with the following subsystem decomposition: motion unit, process unit, spindle head (orthogonal, quill or automatic), rotation transmission system, automatic tool changer, head magazine, spindle head interface, DAS active damper actuator, electrical system, control system and Hydraulic/pneumatic system. The condition of the cutting tool can depend on these subsystems and its operating mode, for instance, on the axes-positioning, the speed of rotation and vibration in the spindle head. Statistical models can help characterize the cutting tools using the CM measures of TP-like health indicators.

The cutting tool has three parts (Figure 20). The change of each part is not automated and is made based on the criteria of the operator. This is unknown until the moment the tool is replaced. This task is not automated and it is performed based on the operator's criteria. Part (3) is not critical, part (2) is replaced in each piece and part (3) every 15-20 pieces.

Figure 20: Parts of cutting tool.

Some of the following valuable information is expected throughout the execution of the PreCoM project:

- time in which the part (1) of the piece is replaced,
- the wear of part (2) and (3) of the tool,
- whether the wear of the tool was the main cause of the machine failure. Until now, the operator of the machine and the maintenance technician have used spreadsheets to enter the maintenance hours in the software and the case of the failure.

In Section 2 of D3.11, TP were defined as a wide range of variables reporting the key information for PdM. Failure times can be understood more generally. For instance, end-users may decide to change a critical component when vibration or another relevant variable overcomes a known threshold. Of course, in such a case the value of the threshold should be specified so the time up to exceeding the threshold can be computed.

5.1.1. Statistical model for cutting tool

The TP are CM every second, so a time series approach is appropriate in this phase of the project. The general structure of the model is described in Eq. (9) but perhaps a simpler model suffices.

$$(Y_{t+\Delta,i} - Y_{t,i}) = \alpha \Delta + z_{t+\Delta} + \theta_1 z_{t+\Delta} + \dots + \theta_q z_{t-q} + \sum \beta_j (X_{t+\delta,j} - \bar{X}_j) \quad (9)$$

where

- Δ : Time since the last time the task i was done,
- $Y_{t+\Delta,i}$: TP level to predict in task i at time t + Δ
- $Y_{t,i}$: Last TP level observed in task i at time t

For $j=1, \dots, J-1$ and $t < t_j + \delta < t + \Delta$, the model includes the difference in the TP between the last two executions of task j, so,

- $X_{t+\delta,j}$: TP observed in task j at time $t_j + \delta$
- X_t : TP observed in task j at time t_j
- $z_{t+\Delta}$: White noise
- θ : Polynomials of degree q (part MA of ARIMA)

The wear on the cutting tool is the variable of interest (similar to the proof of concept). Alternatively, other health indicators associated with the cutting tool (defined in D3.1) could be used, such as the vibration measured in a component.

If the information required by LTA and TSA techniques, as described in the proof of concept, is available, then the following outputs can be provided:

- From TSA the output information will be:
 1. Point and interval prediction of the variable of interest. It requires knowing the wear of cutting tool, otherwise a related variable such as vibration in a component will be used.
 2. The probability that the predicted values overcomes a specified threshold at the time $t+h$ therefore, the time in which the limit will be exceeded will be known.
 3. If observed measurement is much greater than the prediction ($Y_{t+\Delta,i} > \hat{Y}_{t+\Delta,i}$), this can indicate that the wear is greater than expected according to normal working conditions (or that the material is defective, or there is an undetected damage, ...).
- From LTA the output information will be:
 1. Mean residual lifetime. Estimated probability distribution of the remaining operation time of the targeted component.
 2. Future probabilities of failure or stoppage.
 3. Specific quantiles of the residual life.

Traditionally the vibration signals are summarized by statistics such as the mean, standard deviation, range (maximum and minimum), deviation or the root mean square (RMS). However, in the era of Industry 4.0, this paradigm is changing because Big Data Analysis techniques can be applied to take better advantage of the information contained in the signals. If information of baseline pattern of vibration was provided (or estimated), for instance, then the comparison between the new task execution with respect to the baseline pattern could provide alarms on possible failures.

Functional data analysis (FDA) techniques can also be useful in regression frameworks. For example, following with the proof of concept used in Section 2.3 we fit two regression models, the classical linear model (LM) and the functional linear model (FLM) using the flank wear (**VB**) as a response variable. FLM uses the raw signal of **smsDC** as a predictor (see Figure 7) and the adjusted R-squared was $R^2_{adj} = 0.63$, while the LM model used a summary of the **smsDC** signal provided by the RMS

(univariate predictor), obtaining a worse estimated model, $R^2_{adj} = 0.47$. We use the function `lm` of the statistics of the package R and the function `fregre.lm` of the package R `fda.usc`.

5.1.2. Rotating critical components

The analysis made in D7.1 pointed that three main machine's parts are considered to be critical in the FXR machine, for more details see D7.1. These parts are as follow:

1. **Spindle head:** The FXR machine has two spindles in the head magazine i.e. the orthogonal head and modular quill head.
 - a. The orthogonal spindle head: it has an automatic indexing of vertical and horizontal articulations. It is equipped with an automatic tool changing. The cooling system could be internal or external. It is suitable for any type of taper and pull-studs. This spindle can generate different clamping forces for different tools (see Figure 21). The critical components to be monitored are bearings shafts and gears.

Figure 21: Overview of the orthogonal spindle head.

- b. The modular quill head: Compared to traditional quill solutions, the exclusive Soraluze modular quill spindle enables the same distance between the column and the spindle nose for the quill and rest of milling heads, enabling 5-sided machining in the same set-up without any additional re-positioning of the workpiece at a long distance from the machine (See Figure 22). The critical components to be monitored in the quill head are the bearings.

Figure 22: The modular quill spindle head.

2. **Gearbox:** The Soraluze FXR milling boring machine has an integrated gearbox. This means that it is not a commercial gearbox, and cannot be removed or replaced. It is integrated in the Z-Axis (RAM) of the machine. Therefore, if a problem appears it must be solved onsite

and the machine must be stopped. The gearbox is a complex mechanism that contains 11 bearings, 5 pairs of gears and 4 shafts. The critical components to be monitored in the gearbox are considered to be bearings, shafts and gears.

3. **Main motor:** Air-cooled Siemens 1PH7 motors are rugged and low-maintenance 4-pole induction motors with squirrel-cage rotors (See Figure 23: Main motor). A fan for providing forced ventilation is mounted axially on the rear side of the motor. The motors are equipped with an integrated encoder system for sensing the motor speed and indirect position. Rated speed 1500 rpm, and maximum speed 4500 rpm. Rated power for duty type is 130kW (174HP) in S1. The critical components to be monitored in the motor are the bearings and the shaft.

Figure 23: Main motor.

In the reviewed rotating critical components above (spindles, bearings, shafts, gears), vibration monitoring technique is an effective technique to determine the machine/rotating component condition. To achieve this, Smart eMDSS solutions will be used i.e. PreVib will be used to analyse, detect and localize the abnormality, diagnose, follow the damage development and predict the future vibration level. While ProLife will be used to assess the failure probability and residual life per component.

To enable PreVib and ProLife to perform their function the following input information will be necessary. These inputs are as follow (For more information about input parameters, please refer to D3.1):

1. The installation and removal time of components/equipment, to identify history machines/components.
2. IDs for the company, machine and component.
3. Bearing ID to make it easy distinguishing different bearings.
4. Motor size measured in Kw.
5. Number of gearwheels and number of teeth per gearwheel in the gearbox in addition to the input and output speeds.
6. Manufacturer recommendations concerning the maximum allowable level of vibration for the machine and component if available.
7. Measurements arrangement, which includes time and location of sensor measurements.
8. Levels of the normal vibration (when no damage is initiated), potential failure (when damage is initiated and under development) and replacement (the maximum allowable vibration level according to ISO norms and experience). These three levels are to determine when the machine/component is in a normal condition, needs more observations to follow up closely and replacement, respectively.

The output information will be:

1. Diagnosis: Detection, identification and localization of damages
2. Assessment of the damage severity
3. Follow up damage development.
4. Near future prediction, which includes the expected load for the machine and the time of the predicted vibration value. This is to predict the damage development (measured on the vibration level development) in the near future.
5. Recommendation of what to do. (It will greta if you check with D3.1 and D4.1 concerning info parameters)

5.2. Use case 2: SPINEA - Overbeck

After the analysis in D7.3, the critical components to be monitored by vibration condition monitoring technique were identified for the two machines ID400 and LAMB II in SPINEA company.

1. For the ID400, the most critical components were:
 - a. the different spindle heads,
 - b. the workhead spindle,
 - c. and the dressing spindle.
2. And for LAMB II:
 - a. the spindle head system (spindle, bearing and motor),
 - b. the tool magazine system (motor, bearing and gearbox),
 - c. and the Z-axis ballscrew (ballscrew and motor).

All these critical components will be monitored using vibration based monitoring (VBM) techniques.

If the information required by LTA and TSA techniques, as described in the proof of concept, is available, then the following outputs can be provided:

- From TSA the output information will be:
 1. Point and interval prediction of the variable of interest.
 2. The probability that the predicted values overcomes a specified threshold at the time $t+h$ therefore, the time in which the limit will be exceeded will be known.
 3. If observed measurement is much greater than the prediction ($Y_{t+\Delta,i} >> \hat{Y}_{t+\Delta,i}$).
- From LTA the output information will be:
 1. Mean residual lifetime. Estimated probability distribution of the remaining operation time of the targeted component.
 2. Future probabilities of failure or stoppage.
 3. Specific quantiles of the residual life.

5.2.1. Spindle heads and tool magazine

For the ID400, the most critical components were the different spindle heads. They include the four wheelhead spindles/grinding spindles the workhead spindle, and the dressing spindle, for information about the critical parts, please refer to D7.3. The critical components to be monitored are considered to be bearings and spindels. Figure 24 illustrates the position of the spindle heads. The workhead clamps the workpiece while the grinding spindles are machining it. When the grinding wheel of the wheelhead gets worn, the dressing spindle sharpens the wheel again.

Figure 24: Spindle head in machine ID400.

For LAMB II, the most critical components to be monitored by vibration condition monitoring technique are: the spindle head system (spindle, bearing and motor), the tool magazine system (motor, bearing and gearbox), and the Z-axis ballscrew (ballscrew and motor). The latter will be monitored using statistical models, see Section 2. Figure 25 and Figure 26 illustrates these critical components.

Figure 25: Lamb II spindle head and tool magazine.

Figure 26: X and Y axes of the Lamb machine.

Vibration condition monitoring technique is identified to be a very effective tool to monitor the condition of the rotating critical components. To monitor these components using vibration

condition monitoring technique, tools from Smart eMDSS platform will be used. These tools are PreVib and ProLife. PreVib will be used to analyse, detect and localize the abnormality, diagnose, follow the damage development and predict the future vibration level. While ProLife will be used to assess the failure probability and residual life per component.

As described in D5.1.2 above, certain parameters are required to utilize these tools.

5.3. Use case 3: Gomà-Camps - Lantier

The Gomà-Camps Group has two paper machines in La Riba's mill, equipped with Lantier's creping systems for the production of 100% virgin cellulose tissue and recycled tissue, with a total capacity over 60,000 metric ton/per year. In a previous project, a monitoring system was installed in the creping doctor of the machine PM5. In PreCoM, machine PM6 (see Figure 27) will be connected and monitored too.

Figure 27: Tissue mill paper Overview.

According to D7.5, the critical components identified in this use case are:

- Forming cylinder
- Suction press cylinder
 1. Yankee dryer cylinder (motor and a gearbox).
 2. The Yankee cylinder and its bearings.
- Creping doctor.

To maintain the dryer system performance, the tissue manufacturer must pay special attention to the creping doctor and creping blade, the Yankee dryer, the gearbox, bearing and papermaking felt among others.

5.3.1. Creping doctor and creping blade

The blade is one of the most critical components (see Figure 28). The creping blade must be preventively changed depending on the blade type and the type of paper manufactured. See 7.5 for further details of this critical component.

Figure 28: Creping doctor and blade holder.

In Section 2.3.1 of D3.1, basic variables such as temperature, paper speed and vibration are analysed for this study case for a short period of historical data corresponding to the machine PM6 from January 2018 to April 2018.

Currently, WP3 has access to the next basic variables: hood temperature, paper speed and severity/vibration measured using four accelerometers. The statistical analysis of these variables is provided below.

Statistical model for creping doctor and creping blade

The creping blade is periodically removed to be cleaned or replaced by a new one, in order to reduce the vibration level. See Figures 29 and 30, where the vibration levels (m/s^2_{rms}) reported by accelerometer 4 along 4.35 days (6265 minutes) are depicted. In these figures, removal times are indicated by vertical dashed lines. After each removal of the blade, it is relevant to anticipate the time until vibration exceeds a user-supplied threshold, which can be regarded as a failure or malfunction of the blade. TSA and LTA models described in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 and later applied to the proof of concept may be used to predict the vibration level or the residual lifetime of the blade. For the accuracy of the predictions, it would be very convenient if the end user may register and provide working conditions such as product being manufactured or other potential stress factors.

WP3 has no access to information on, for instance, kind of paper being manufactured or product quality and failures/stoppages variables. WP7 will register these variables during the PreCoM project. However, since 25 September 2018 it provides the instant when the blade is replaced. Figure 29 shows the 5 blade changes along (18-09-25 14:25:31) to (18-09-29 23:59:59) period.

Figure 29: CM evolution of vibration level in accelerometer 4 (in black) measured in m/s^2rms and times where the blade was changed (vertical dashed red lines).

In addition, the instant in which the blade is cleaned is also registered. This usually affects the level of the vibration of a jump down (see Figure 30).

Figure 30: CM evolution of vibration level in accelerometer 4 (in black) measured in m/s^2rms and times where the blade was cleaned (vertical dotted blue lines).

Vibration level in one accelerometer can be a health indicator to predict the time in which the vibration will exceed a threshold using TSA (following the guidance used in proof of concept). This requires a larger sample of data, and the availability of other TP like the kind of product and product quality.

If the required information is available or estimated empirically from the data, the following outputs can be provided:

- From TSA:
 1. Point and interval prediction of the variable of interest.
 2. The probability that the predicted values overcomes a specific threshold at the time $t + h$; therefore the time in which the limit is exceeded will be known.
 3. If observed measurement is much greater than the prediction made ($Y_{t+\Delta,i} >> \hat{Y}_{t+\Delta,i}$).
- From LTA:

1. Mean residual lifetime. Estimated probability distribution of the remaining operation time of the targeted component.
2. Future probabilities of failure or stoppage.
3. Specific quantiles of the residual life.

5.3.2. Rotating critical components

In D7.5 an analysis is conducted to identify the critical components to be monitored using vibration-based maintenance (VBM) (see D7.5 for more information).

These components are:

1. Forming cylinder: The forming cylinder power transmission is composed of two parts:
 - a. A motor and a gearbox: The forming cylinder has two spherical roller bearings at each end of the cylinder (see Figure 31).
 - b. The cylinder and its bearings: The cylinder has two spherical roller bearings at each end of the cylinder (see Figure 32).

Figure 31: Forming power transmission gearbox.

Figure 32: Forming cylinder bearings.

2. Suction press cylinder: The suction press cylinder has two spherical roller bearings; one at drive side bearing and one at the driven side. Figure 33 illustrates the suction press roll bearings.

Figure 33: Suction press roll bearings.

3. Yankee dryer cylinder: The main power transmission of the tissue paper mill is conducted by the gear transmission of the Yankee dryer cylinder. The Yankee dryer power transmission is composed of two parts:
 - a. A motor and a gearbox: The gearbox has three shafts and two pair of gears to transmit the power (see Figure 34).

Figure 34: Yankee power transmission gearbox.

- b. The Yankee cylinder and its bearings: The bearings in the Yankee dryer section are exposed to very high temperatures over long periods of time. Unfavourable lubrication conditions are quite common and short start-up periods cause very high thermal stresses in the bearings. Therefore, the operating conditions for these bearings are quite severe. Over the years the demands made on the bearings have also increased due to larger machines, higher speeds and higher steam temperatures (Figure 35).

Figure 35: Yankee cylinder bearings.

These rotating critical components will be monitored by vibration condition monitoring technique using PreVib and ProLife software tools. PreVib and ProLife will be used to analyse, detect and localize the abnormality, diagnose, follow the damage development and predict the future vibration level, assess the failure probability and residual life.

To apply PreVib and ProLife to these components properly, the input information parameters mentioned in Sec. 5.2 are required (For more information about input parameters, please refer to D3.1 and D4.1).

6. Failure mode, effects, and critically analysis (FMECA)

We will use Failure Mode Effects and Criticality Analysis (FMECA) and Failure Time Analysis (FTA) models to systematically identify machine top problems, partition a machine, analyse component failures (identify root-causes, effects on system operations and components' criticalities) and identify significant components (components of dangerous or expensive failures) to provide effective maintenance efforts on right components.

For SAKANA, D7.1 contains information about the identification of the most critical components according to the FMECA analysis developed by the machine-tool manufacturer. D7.1 identifies the main systems and subsystems of the machine is composed, and proposed collect past historical problems/failures of the proposed machine and analyse historical maintenance services data.

The Failure Modes and Effect Analysis (FMEA) is a systematic procedure for the analysis of a system to identify the potential failure modes, their causes and effects on system performance to include a means of ranking the severity of the failure modes to allow prioritization of countermeasures.

The top rated critical components considered in the evaluation of the FMECA analysis are the following:

- Spindle quill head,
- Orthogonal and automatic spindle heads
- Main gearbox of the transmission system.
- The main spindle motor.

The secondary critical components are related basically to the XYZ machine axes in motion transmission. Finally, the automatic tool changer and the hydraulic unit are considered not critical.

The FMECA analysis will be should label according to the 4 severity of the potential failure mode: Catastrophic (Rank 4), Critical (Rank 3), Marginal (Rank 2), Minor (Rank 1). Therefore, it is proposed to establish a dynamic table in which the number of events in each range is collected for each critical component. The occurrence of potential root causes may also be classified in one of the following categories: (1) remote, when only isolated failures associated with this process or almost identical processes, (2) low when the process has occasional failures, but not in major proportions, (3) moderate when the process or similar processes have often failed and (4) high when failure is almost inevitable. Finally, as far as possible, the detection scale (absolute, very low, moderate or almost certain) measured by the company should be taken into account.

7. Conclusions

In this document, we have described and illustrated statistical models that can improve diagnosis and prognosis for the three demo-companies in PreCoM.

We have applied the proposed statistical methodology to two well-known data sets: MIMOSA dataset and Mill dataset. These proofs of concept indicate that the proposed statistical developments will be useful for:

- predicting the vibration level in the near future (using Time Series Analysis and PreVib software module) as way for assessing the replacement of critical components;
- assessing the failure probability and remaining lifetime of a component (using Life Time Analysis and ProLife software module).

The main conclusion is that better quality and data coverage reduces the uncertainty in the predicted value of the vibration level used to describe the condition of a significant component, especially when the deviation in its life length is mostly related to the operating conditions. This would reduce the number and duration of planned and unplanned stoppage that has a direct impact on the company's productivity, and hence, its competitiveness.

Appendix: Mill data set description

Table 11: Experimental conditions.

Case	Depth of Cut	Feed	Material
1	1,5	0,5	1 – cast iron
2	0,75	0,5	1 – cast iron
3	0,75	0,25	1 – cast iron
4	1,5	0,25	1 – cast iron
5	1,5	0,5	2 – steel
6	1,5	0,25	2 – steel
7	0,75	0,25	2 – steel
8	0,75	0,5	2 – steel
9	1,5	0,5	1 – cast iron
10	1,5	0,25	1 – cast iron
11	0,75	0,25	1 – cast iron
12	0,75	0,5	1 – cast iron
13	0,75	0,25	2 – steel
14	0,75	0,5	2 – steel
15	1,5	0,25	2 – steel
16	1,5	0,5	2 – steel

Table 12: Data description for mill dataset.

Variable name	Description
case	Case number (1-16)
run	Counter for experimental runs in each case
VB	Flank wear, measured after runs; Measurements for VB were not taken after each run
time	Duration of experiment (restarts for each case)
DOC	Depth of cut (does not vary for each case)
feed	Feed (does not vary for each case)
material	Material (does not vary for each case)
smcAC	AC spindle motor current
smcDC	DC spindle motor current
vib_table	Table vibration
vib_spindle	Spindle vibration
AE_table	Acoustic emission at table
AE_spindle	Acoustic emission at spindle

Table 13: Results for time series analysis for model 3).

Model	Material A			Material B		
	LB test	MSE in train	MSE in prediction	LB test	MSE in train	MSE in prediction
ARIMA(1,0,0)	0.615	1.4610	9.3278	0.273	1.2345	0.4301
ARIMAX(1,0,0)	0.992	1.7887	0.2934	0.891	0.0574	1.4096
ARIMAX(1,1,0)	0.864	0.1998	0.8549	0.660	0.0613	0.2458

Figure 36: Control chart of estimated residuals (calibration data) and predictions (test data) for model 3) in material A (left panel) and material B (right panel) using indirect indicator as response.

Table 14: Formulas for acronyms.

Acronim	Formula
RMS continous time domain	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{\Delta T} \int_0^{\Delta T} f^2(t) dt}$
RMS discrete time domain	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (f(t_k))^2}$
R ²	$1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2}$
Residual	$e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$
MSE	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2$
Δy	$y_i - y_{i-1}$

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